

Case series on management of Coronary Artery Disease, Hypertension and Post Myocardial Infarct Patient through *Hridaya Basti*.

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Abstract

Basti is a major therapy among *Snehadi Karma* in *Panchkarma*. It works as *Samshodhana* & *Samsamana* because of combination of different drugs. The external *Basti* includes *Shirobasti*, *Hridaya Basti*, *Kati Basti*, *Jaanu Basti* etc. *Hridaya Basti* also known as *Uro Basti*. In *Ayurveda Urah Pradesh* is a seat of *Pranvaha Srotasa* and *Kapha Dosha*. It is a centre of flow of blood in body & cardio-respiratory functions. *Hridaya* is also termed as *Mula Sthana* of *Rasavaha*, *Pranvaha* & *Manovaha Srotasa*. So basically *Uro Basti* is given at the centre of chest in various cardio-pulmonary diseases. Now a day where people are pampered to high caloric diet, saturated fat rich diet & many other violations of principles of diet cause biofire insufficiency. As an insufficient bio fire *Aama Rasa* (hyperlipidemia) is formed which further leads to *Dhamni Praticaya* (thickening of vessels) & *Dhamni Kathinya* (hardening). Finally the *Srotorodha* occurs & manifest as *Ruja* (angina) or many more disease of cardiopulmonary system. So we have to correct the biofire and *rasa Samvahana*. In *Uro Basti* medicated liquid is poured over the sternum which gives *Swedana* effect to the local structures especially to the aorta. Dilatation of vessel occurs & flow of blood is maintained. As a result it gives relief in symptoms and strengthens the muscle.

Keywords: *Panchkarma*; *Hridaya Basti*; *Hridaya*; *Pranvaha Srotasa*

1. Introduction

Basti therapy is of two types, one is internal and another one is external. The internal *Basti* includes *Niruha*, *Anuvasana* & the external *Basti* which is also called *Sthanika Basti* includes *Shirobasti*, *Hridaya Basti*, *Kati Basti*, *Jaanu Basti* etc. *Hridaya Basti* also known as *Uro Basti* because it is given at *Urah Pradesh* over the sternum. *Hridaya Basti* is a *Sthanika Basti* used in *Hridaya Roga* and various other disease of *Urah Pradesh*. In *Hridaya Basti* luke warm decoction/ medicated oil is poured over the *Urah Pradesh* to maintain the *Rasa Samvahan* (circulation). It is an external approach to many cardio-pulmonary diseases by maintaining the proper flow of blood. It is commonly used in pain condition. It also has beneficial effect on mind and gives strengthening effect to cardiac muscle.

Objective

- To access the outcomes of *Hridaya Basti* in various cardiovascular diseases.
- To access the outcomes of *Hridaya Basti* as a therapy to improve the quality of life by increasing the functional capacity of the heart.

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2. Literature review

- The word *Basti* derived from the “*Vasa*” *Dhatu*, coated as “*Vas Nivase*” (reside), “*Vas Achadane*” (to cover)¹
- In general, there are two approach of *Basti* therapy one is internal and another one is external. The internal *Basti* includes *Niruha*, *Anuvasana* & the external *Basti* which is also called *Sthanika Basti* includes *Shirobasti*, *Hridaya Basti*, *Kati Basti*, *Jaanu Basti* etc.
- *Hridaya Basti* also known as *Uro Basti* because it is given at *Urah Pradesh* over the sternum.
- In *Ayurveda* *Hridaya* is also termed as *Mula Sthana* of *Rasavaha*, *Pranvaha* & *Manovaha Srotasa*.

3. Material and methods

Table 1 Material Needed for *Hridaya Basti*

Material	Quantity
<i>Masha</i> Powder	800gm
<i>Medicated Taila</i>	500ml
Cotton roll	1
Vessel	4
Towel	2
Cotton ribbon	1

3.1. Site

At the center of chest by taking mediastinum as a center point.

3.2. Procedure

3.2.1. Pre-operative Procedure:

Patient should be lie in comfortable supine position exposition the chest. If the site is hairy, it must be shaved clearly. Gently massage the area & *Hasta Swedana* should be done. After that rub that area from dry powder for opening the pores. Dough of thick consistency is prepared with *Masha choorna* flour by adding water^{2,3}. This is rolled to a long strap, with the height about three *Angulas* and width of one inch. The length should be sufficient to form a ring around the area. The ends are fixed such that it forms a loop. Now the *Paali* is attached firmly over the chest region, & the edges should be sealed with thin paste of *Masha choorna*, ensuring that the content should not leak from container. Place cotton pad at the centre of brim on the surface to avoid direct contact of hot oil.

3.2.2. Main Procedure Steps

- The medicated oil is warmed, and is poured from the side over *the urah pradesh* within *palli* for 30-45 min.
- It should be noticed that the temperature of medicated oil should be maintained by changing medicated oil with help of cotton as per need.
- After the prescribed time, medicated oil is to be removed off from over the chest with the help of cotton.

3.2.3. Post Procedure Steps

Remove the dough. Wipe the surface with cotton or towel. Patient is advised to take rest in the same position for 10-20 min

4. Result

4.1. Case report :1

A 56 years old male patient resident of Badibrahmna Jammu comes with complaints of mild chest pain radiating to left arm, palpitation, fatigue since 1 week.

After detailed examination and investigation, he was diagnosed with coronary artery disease

4.1.1. Management Done

Hridaya basti done with *kshara taila* on alternative days for 21 days.

Shaman aushadis :-

- *Hrudya vati* 1000 mg 2 times a day before food.
- *Anarsha Kshara* 3 pinch before food.
- *Sukha virechana Churna* 1tsb after food.

4.2. Case report: 2

A 48 years old male patient resident of Nardini Jammu comes with complaints of severe headache and vomitings. He is known case of hypertension since 5 years on evaluation his BP found is 180/90 mm of hg inspite taking allopathic mediciene.

4.2.1. Management Done

Hridaya basti done with *Dhanvantar Taila* on alternative days for 14 days.

Shaman aushadis :-

- *Prabhaker vati* 2BD (A/ M) with water.
- *Punarnava mandoor* 2BD (A/ M) with water
- *Sukha virechana Churna* 1tsb after food.

4.3. Case report :- 3

A 65 years old female patient resident of Satwari Jammu comes with complaints of mild to moderate chest pain radiating to right arm, palpitation, fatigue, mild dyspnea from 5 months. Known case of myocardial infarction (attack before 3 years).

She was diagnosed as post MI Angina

4.3.1. Management Done

Hridaya basti done with *Chandana Bala Lakshadi taila* on alternative days for 21 days.

Shaman aushadis :-

- *Hrudya vati* 1000 mg 2 times a day before food.
- *Anarsha Kshara* 3 pinch before food.
- *Sukha virechana Churna* 1tsb after food.

4.4. Result

Table 2 Result

Patient 1	Before treatment,patient presented with complaints of mild chest pain radiating to left arm, palpitation, fatigue since 1 week	After treatment for 21 days, patient shows marked improvement in chest pain, palpitation, fatigue
Patient 2	Before treatment,patient presented with complaints of severe headache and vomitings and elevated bp ranging 180/90 mm of hg.	After treatment for 14 days, patients headache and vomiting subsides and bp comes in range of 130/90 mm of hg.
Patient 3	Before treatment,patient presented with complaints of mild to moderate chest pain radiating to right arm, palpitation, fatigue,	After treatment for 21 days, patient shows marked improvement in chest

	mild dyspnea from 5 months. Known case of myocardial infarction (attack before 3 years).	pain, palpitation, fatigue, mild dyspnea
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5. Discussion

In *Hridaya Basti*, after the application of hot medicated oil, penetration of heat through the skin started, which not only dilate the blood vessel (aorta) but also stimulates the receptor of vagus nerve (intrinsic nervous system) through heart – brain communication & mind become calm. Generalized metabolic reaction of drug is also occurs at that area. Finally gives the result as proper *Rasa Samvahana* (circulation), calm effect on brain & also strengthen the cardiac muscles.

According to *Ayurveda* it maintains the flow of *Rasa Dhatu* enhances the *Hridaya Sthana Gata Pitta Karma* & regulates the *Vyan Vata*. Proper *Rasa Samvahana* nourishes the *Hridaya Pradesh*.

In *Hridya Roga*, the function of *Ras Dhatu* is hampered by vitiated *Doshas* situated in the *Hridya*. Through *Hridya Basti* mild *Swedana* is given which control the vitiated *Vata-Kapha* & the function of *Rasa Samvahana* becomes proper. It also gives relief in pain as pain is caused by *Vata* & *Swedana* is the primary treatment modality of vitiated *Vata Dosha*.

In Hypertension, improper blood supply to body & heart due to vessel constriction occurs. The *Hridya Basti* on the chest region will dilate the aorta & maintain the blood flow.

In CAD the pathway becomes narrow due to atherosclerosis which causes improper blood supply to heart. In this situation the *Hridya Basti* correct the flow of blood to heart by dilating the blood vessels.

6. Conclusion

- *Hridaya Basti* is local application of medicated oil over a specific area of chest. It enhances the blood flow, strengthens the muscles & also reduces the stress & anxiety through brain- heart communication.
- It can be used in various cardio vascular disease like hypertension, Post MI, CAD etc.
- It can be used as a therapy to improve the quality of life by increasing the functional capacity of the heart.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No the conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of ethical approval

Ethical approval was obtained.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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